

How Image Segmentation Affects Classification: Implications in a Cancer Diagnostic Model

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Abstract

This study investigates how segmentation impacts the performance of Vision Transformer (ViT) models in classifying histopathological images. We trained ViT on segmented images using the DigestPath dataset with expert-annotated masks and the BACH dataset with generated masks, and then tested the model on unsegmented images. We compared the accuracy of this pipeline with another pipeline where the training was conducted on unsegmented images. Our results showed that segmentation affected classification differently depending on the dataset. In DigestPath, training on segmented images led to lower accuracy (62.12%) compared to unsegmented training (83.33%), likely due to overfitting on highly accurate ground-truth masks. Conversely, in BACH, training on segmented images improved accuracy (81.25% vs. 76.25%), suggesting that less accurate masks could enhance generalizability. These findings highlight the nuanced impact of image segmentation on the performance of classification models, particularly in histopathological image analysis.

Context and Background

The application of computer vision in medical fields has been instrumental in addressing complex real-world problems (Esteva et al., 2021). One of the most challenging areas where computer vision can make a substantial impact is histopathology, where tissue samples are examined microscopically to diagnose diseases such as cancer (Chang & Hatfield, 2024; Jiang et al., 2020).

Histopathology images are uniquely challenging due to their high resolution, variable staining protocols, and complex tissue architecture. Identifying tumor regions within these images is particularly difficult because of overlapping features between malignant and benign areas. Traditional manual interpretation is not only time-consuming but also prone to inter-observer variability and errors. Computer vision techniques, such as image classification and segmentation, provide powerful tools to aid pathologists in these tasks (Lu et al., 2024; Wu et al., 2022).

Recent advancements in deep learning, particularly with state-of-the-art segmentation models, e.g. Segment Anything Model (SAM) (Kirillov et al., 2023) and its derivatives fine-tuned on medical images such as Med-SAM (Ma et al., 2024), can potentially enable efficient and precise delineation of tumor regions within histopathological images (Deng et al., 2025; Wang et al., 2024). These models, especially when fine-tuned and carefully implemented, can allow for a more targeted analysis by focusing on biologically relevant areas of the tissue (Ali et al., 2024; Chauveau & Merville, 2023). Vision Transformer (ViT) models (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020), originally designed for natural image classification, have emerged as a promising alternative to

convolutional neural networks (CNNs) in medical imaging due to their ability to capture long-range dependencies within images (Azad et al., 2024).

We hypothesized that training a ViT model on segmented histopathological images, where non-tumor regions are dimmed, would enhance its ability to focus on diagnostically important features. By doing so, the model might learn more relevant representations, improving classification performance. However, evaluating this approach requires careful consideration, as the segmentation process itself may introduce biases or remove potentially informative contextual features.

Approach

We conducted a comparative analysis of ViT performance when trained on segmented versus when trained on unsegmented histopathology images to assess whether segmentation improves the model's ability to distinguish tumor from normal tissues when tested on original unsegmented images.

Datasets

We used two publicly available histopathology datasets: DigestPath (Da et al., 2022) and BACH (Aresta et al., 2019). The DigestPath challenge dataset consists of H&E-stained histopathology images from 410 normal and 250 cancerous colon tissue. These images are annotated at the pixel level, and the dataset provides expert-annotated ground-truth segmentation masks delineating tumor regions. The BreAst Cancer Histology (BACH) dataset includes H&E-stained breast tissue images, categorized into four classes: normal, benign, in situ carcinoma, and invasive carcinoma. Unlike DigestPath, the BACH dataset does not include ground-truth segmentation masks for all

images. To overcome this limitation, we employed SAM to generate masks that highlight areas of interest in the images.

Preprocessing and Experimental Setup

We began by separating tumor and normal images in both datasets and then split them into 80% training and 20% testing sets. We created two distinct versions of the training dataset: a segmented dataset and an unsegmented dataset.

In the segmented dataset, tumor images were processed using binary masks, either provided by the dataset authors (Figure 1a) or generated using SAM (Figure 1b), to retain tumor regions while dimming the non-tumor areas. Normal images, which lack distinct tumor regions, were uniformly dimmed by the same dimming factor.

The unsegmented dataset, in contrast, consisted of the original, unmodified images, allowing us to examine the impact of training on masked images on the model’s ability to identify key histopathological features.

Model and Theoretical Framework

We leveraged the base Google ViT model, which processes images as sequences of patches, capturing long-range dependencies more effectively than convolutional neural networks (CNNs).

To ensure the appropriate transformations are applied, we utilized a ViTImageProcessor configured based on the settings stored alongside the pretrained model. For this study, we used a pre-trained ViT model, the “google/vit-base-patch16-224-in21k” model, and retrieved its corresponding image processor from the Hugging Face Hub, and fine-tuned it on our datasets using an input size of 224×224 pixels, and a batch size of 16.

Implementation Details

We fine-tuned the `google/vit-base-patch16-224-in21k` model using the Hugging Face `transformers` library (4.51.3) and PyTorch (2.6.0+cu124). Images were resized to 224×224, and processed using the corresponding `ViTImageProcessor`. Training was conducted on a single NVIDIA Tesla T4 GPU using Google Colab. We fine-tuned the model using the Hugging Face `Trainer` API with default settings. The learning rate was set to 2e-4, and we trained for 20 epochs with a batch size of 16. No class weights were applied.

Experiments and Analysis

We conducted multiple training runs to compare the model's performance under different conditions (Figure 1c). For `digestPath` using ground-truth masks, we first trained the model on segmented images with non-tumor areas in the tumor images, and the whole area in the normal images dimmed. We tested the model on unsegmented original images, and the model reached an accuracy of 62.12%. We then trained the model on a mixed dataset using both segmented and unsegmented images, and again tested the model on unsegmented original images. Using this method, the accuracy improved to 86.36%. Using a mixed dataset, the accuracy approximately reached the obtained accuracy when training the model was conducted on unsegmented tumor and normal images, which was 83.33%.

As mentioned earlier, we used generated masks for BACH dataset. The segmentation was done using SAM, with "inverted segmentation" applied, i.e. where the inverse of the segmentation mask created was considered and applied to specify the subject/region of interest. When training was done on unsegmented data, the model achieved a test accuracy of 76.25%. On the other

hand, training on segmented data achieved the highest test accuracy of 81.25%. This suggests that the model trained on segmented data generalizes well to unsegmented test data.

Segmentation Evaluation

We quantitatively evaluated the segmentation performance of both SAM and MedSAM on the DigestPath dataset using Dice coefficient, Intersection over Union (IoU), and accuracy. SAM outperformed MedSAM in all three metrics, achieving an average Dice score of 0.398, IoU of 0.273, and accuracy of 0.643, compared to MedSAM's 0.336 Dice, 0.217 IoU, and 0.328 accuracy (Figure 1d).

Discussion and conclusion

For the DigestPath dataset, where expert-annotated ground-truth masks were available, training on segmented images resulted in a significant drop in test accuracy (62.12%), which improved to 86.36% when both segmented and unsegmented images were included in training, and was comparable to the accuracy (83.33%) achieved when training was done on unsegmented images. These findings suggest that the model may have overfitted to the highly accurate ground-truth masks, resulting in poor generalization when tested on unsegmented images.

In contrast, for the BACH dataset, where segmentation masks were generated using SAM, with an approximate segmentation accuracy of 60% , a different pattern emerged. The model trained on unsegmented images achieved 76.25% test accuracy, but when trained on segmented images and tested on unsegmented data, the accuracy increased to 81.25%. Unlike DigestPath, the generated masks were not 100% accurate, and this likely introduced some variability into the training process. The segmentation model failed to capture the exact tumor boundaries, leaving

some background information intact. This imperfection in segmentation appeared to allow it to learn features that were still useful when applied to unsegmented images.

In conclusion, segmentation does not always improve classification performance and, in some cases, can even hinder generalization. The key factor influencing this outcome is the accuracy and completeness of segmentation masks. When using highly accurate ground-truth masks, the model tended to overfit to the segmented regions, leading to poorer performance when tested on unsegmented images. In contrast, when using generated masks with lower segmentation accuracy, the model appeared to generalize better, likely due to residual background information preventing overfitting. This suggests that segmentation should not be viewed as a universally beneficial preprocessing step but rather as a technique whose effectiveness depends on how it is applied and the quality of the masks used. Further research is needed to determine the ideal balance between segmentation accuracy and generalizability in different datasets.

Figure 1. Examples of the preprocessed images and model performance.

a) An example of an original tumor image, its provided ground truth mask, and the final segmented image from the DigestPath dataset. b) An example of an original image, its generated mask using SAM, and the final segmented image from the BACH dataset. c) The model performance trained on the segmented images and tested on the unsegmented images, or trained and tested on the unsegmented images from the BACH and DigestPatch datasets. d) Segmentation accuracies using SAM or MedSAM model on the DigestPath dataset.

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